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Numerical Simulation of A Fission Chain Reaction in a 2D Nuclear Pile

BSc Theoretical Project

submitted to
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March 2024

Abstract

This project uses an own-built Monte Carlo Neutron Transport model to simulate the system dynamics of a 2D nuclear reactor pile undergoing thermal-neutron fission. The interactions between neutrons and pile components; fissile fuel and moderating materials are modelled to achieve the condition of steady-state energy output. Through recording of neutron histories and interaction outcomes, the Monte Carlo method serves as a useful and reliable reconstruction tool to replicate and analyse reactor processes. Based on a control configuration that most resembles a critical state, the report investigates the impact that varying pile dimensions and pile geometries have on reactor dynamics, namely the influences on neutron reproduction factors.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Report Structure

This introduction section provides a brief background into nuclear fission. The methods section follows with an outline of the Monte Carlo Neutron Transport Model design used. The analysis section presents the findings from the project's MC method; firstly it examines different fission probabilities for achieving reactor criticality; then for such steady-state fission settings, different parameter influences such as grid sizes are used to examine variances; lastly, results on how pile component geometries and density arrangements relate to system-state outputs, are examined. A brief section is given for discussion on computational times, ensuing with the report's conclusions. The code for the project's Monte Carlo Neutron Transport model is available in the Appendices section.

1.2 Monte Carlo for Nuclear Fission

Since the term *Uranspaltung* (Uranium fission) was coined in Hahn and Strassman's paper in 1939 [1] – where the plausibility of nuclear fission chain reactions were realised – quick progress arose in achieving self-sustaining reactor piles. During World War II, scientists at the Manhattan Project faced challenges in analysing thermonuclear scenarios. Mathematical methods of that period to predict the state of a chain reactor system, required solving partial differential equations with high-degrees of freedom & closed form solutions. In essence, manual calculations were not possible. To decide if their pile arrangements would lead to successful thermonuclear scenarios, Stanislaw Ulam and Enrico Fermi devised the Monte Carlo (MC) approach [2]. Whilst the former was playing a game of Solitaire, it occurred to him that the expected card outcome could be obtained – through the Law of Large Numbers – by repeatedly recording a large number of independent games and tallying their result distributions. Together they figured to apply statistical sampling methods to determine the reactor dynamics, namely by tallying the histories of neutron transportation paths & their interactions.

Similarly, this project uses a Monte Carlo method in action, to qualitatively reproduce simple reactor dynamics and to capture expected outcomes and statistical variances. Through the use of parametric analysis, where all-but-one system parameters are fixed, insights into the partial relationships that govern the behavior of reactors are obtained. Relationships such as total neutron loss intensity as a function of increasing pile sizes; or k-factors as a function of fuel-to-moderator arrangements are later discussed.

1.3 Understanding Nuclei Stability & Fission Energy Release

To explain why fission occurs, consider the nucleus of an atom as an incompressible water droplet held in place by its binding energy. For each nucleon constituting the 'droplet', the strong nuclear force (that which binds) acts attractively on every nearest neighbour, with each of these correspondingly assumed to be in contact with an equal amount – excluding the boundary nucleons which have less neighbours to interact with (this can be thought of as the surface tension). As strong nuclear forces are short-ranged, this positive binding energy component is approximately linearly proportional to the nucleus's volume, or namely, the mass number (A). On the contrary, one has Coulomb repulsive forces acting between the protons, lessening the value of the binding energy. Unlike the former, these repulsive forces extend over larger distances. As every proton interacts not only with its immediate neighbours but with all other protons in the nucleus, this negative component to the binding energy is proportional to the square of the atomic number (Z^2). As nuclei get heavier, the repulsion component outmatches the strong nuclear force, hence, becoming less stable and of smaller binding energies i.e. less tightly bound. As illustrated in Figure 1.1; when hit by a neutron, these absorb sufficient energy to overcome the binding energy; they become excited and deform in a similar manner to how a water droplet would after being disturbed. Such deformation can lead to an elongated shape (scission) where the aforementioned surface tension component grows enough to split the nucleon.

Figure 1.1 Illustration of nuclear fission shapes as per the liquid drop model, adapted from 'Introductory Nuclear Physics' by Kenneth S. Krane (p. 484, Figure 13.5) [3]

Parent nuclei have less mass than the sum of their individual nucleons, with this missing mass corresponding to the binding energy that holds it (mass-energy equivalence). In the process of fission going from an unstable nucleus – less binding energy per nucleon and more mass per nucleon – to a more stable state, with more binding energy per nucleon and less mass per nucleon, results in a loss of mass. This reduction, accounting for the tighter bonds, leads to the conversion and release of energy, manifested in the form of the kinetic energy of the two fission fragments and ν neutrons, where ν is the average number of neutrons emitted. The latter is probabilistic in nature however tends to range between 2 and 3 neutrons; for the U^{235} used in this project simulation, $\nu = 2.43$. Meanwhile, the binding energy per nucleon of U^{235} is about 7.6 MeV. As outlined by Equation 1.1, for the typical fission fragments, Sr^{94} and Xe^{140} , with binding energies per nucleon of 8.6 MeV and 8.3 MeV respectively [4], one has $(-235 \times 7.6) = -1786$ MeV nucleus binding energy at U^{235} and $((-94 \times 8.6) + (-140 \times 8.3)) = -1970.4$ MeV binding energy for the fragments. The difference of 1970.4 MeV - 1786 MeV = 184.4 MeV

is the amount of energy released from the mass defect.

1.4 Fission Cross Sections & Chain Reactions

Not all neutron-nucleon collisions lead to fission, sometimes these are scattered and at other times these are simply absorbed by the nuclei. The probability of fission occurring is quantified by the 'cross-section' of the nucleus, a term analogous to the effective area that a target nucleus presents to an incoming neutron. For different isotopes, the cross-section depends on the momentum of the neutron – e.g. for U^{235} the cross-section is much higher for slow (thermal) neutrons, owing to how slower neutrons exhibit longer wavelengths that resonate with U^{235} vacant nucleon energy levels (shells), causing nuclei scission. This effect is crucial in thermal-neutron reactors, where one of the key processes involves the use of moderator cells to "thermalise" neutrons enough to cause fission. These moderator cells consist of materials, such as graphite, of similar nuclei mass to the neutrons, that in essence, are placed to result in elastic collisions where maximum momentum is transferred, to effectively "slow down" the neutron.

With a single U^{235} fission event resulting in an expected 2.43 neutrons, a next neutron-nucleus interaction – i.e. a *generation step* or *transport walk* – could result in another fission event, and so on. For whether a chain reaction materialises or not, consider the history of a fission neutron as it undergoes successive neutron transport walks; for it to yet again induce fission, it must first be thermalised through the pass of moderator cells, but crucially, it must do so before being absorbed or leaked from the reactor core. This ratio between neutron-loss and thermalisation probabilities is the key that determines the dynamics of a system. One useful measure to characterise fission reactivity by, is the the neutron reproduction factor k . It essentially represents the average amount of subsequent fission events that an induced neutron will go on to generate, before being lost from the system. As outlined in Equation 1.2, it is measured by the ratio of neutrons in one generation to the amount in the preceding generation of the reaction chain:

$$k = \frac{\text{number of neutrons in one generation}}{\text{number of neutrons in preceding generation}} = \frac{N(t)}{N(t-1)}, \quad (1.2)$$

such that a chain-reaction implies a k -factor ≥ 1 . If $k = 1$ the reactor is said to be in *criticality*, that is, where the system achieved an equilibrium between neutron loss and neutron generation, such that $N(t)$ stays the same (steady-state). If $k > 1$ the neutron counts are growing exponentially, the system is said to be in *supercriticality*; conversely, if $k < 1$ the system is in *subcriticality*, resulting in a chain reaction shutdown. Note that due to the small time constants associated with the reproduction process (around 0.1s), neutron counts can increase by a factor of 22,000 within a matter of one second ($e^{1/0.1}$) [5]. To prevent uncontrolled chain reactions, control rod mechanisms – which consist of highly neutron absorbing materials – are slid into reactor cores to subdue supercriticality scenarios.

CHAPTER 2

Methods

2.1 Simulation Premises

For the purpose of the project's simulation, a basic 2D nuclear pile is conceived such that only the cross-section of the reactor's core is considered. The pile has cells fully packing the grid, representing either fuel rods or moderators. Individual neutrons (which are modelled to only be of two types, either "fast" or "slow") execute a random walk on the grid repeatedly for N generations, with this N amount being arbitrarily assigned in the algorithm's configuration setting. A neutron's diffusion direction is restricted solely to the eight nearest neighbours (NN) and is sampled uniformly at random. These abstractions differ from a real reactor, where: neutron diffusions can extend to any length in the pile, as governed by their momentum, and where neutron speed ranges are not binary, but rather follow a Boltzmann distribution. Other notable model simplifications; fuel cells are not considered depletable during reactions – typically fissile material percentages drop; and decay products, neutron poisoning effects, and delayed neutrons are not considered. In reference to a neutron from the project simulation, depending on its "fast or thermal" label and the type of cell that it finds itself in, certain interactions can occur, with defined probabilities outlined in Table 2.1. As stated; $P(N)$

	Fuel Cell	Moderator cell
Fast Neutron	$P(N N_{\text{fast}} \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.995$	$P(N N_{\text{fast}} \rightarrow C_m) = 0.915$
	$P(A N_{\text{fast}} \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.005$	$P(A N_{\text{fast}} \rightarrow C_m) = 0.005$
		$P(T N_{\text{fast}} \rightarrow C_m) = 0.080$
Slow Neutron	$P(N N_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.545$	$P(N N_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow C_m) = 0.995$
	$P(A N_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.005$	$P(A N_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow C_m) = 0.005$
	$P(F N_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.450$	

Table 2.1 Example of a Possible Probability Set of Neutron Interactions.

indicates the probability of no interaction event occurring apart from diffusion during a given generation step; $P(A)$ refers to the probability of neutron absorption that results in a loss (no fission); $P(T)$ refers to the thermalisation chance when landing on a moderator cell (only fast neutrons can thermalise); and $P(F)$ is the probability of a slow neutron to undergo a fission event when landing on a fuel cell – whereby 2 or 3 neutrons are produced, ($P(F_{2n} = 0.7)$), $P(F_{3n} = 0.3)$) respectively, ($\nu = 2.3$).

Figure 2.1 Illustration of a random walk motion sampled for one simulation run of the Monte Carlo Neutron Transport model algorithm. Consisting of $N = 90$ generation steps on a two-dimensional 13×13 grid. Fuel, Moderator and Boundary cells are shaded in grey, white, and black, respectively; red dots represent fast neutrons and blue dots represent slow neutrons. The latter is exemplified with a larger dot size to represent its larger fission-causing cross-section. Random walk motions are illustrated by arrows where the yellow cell indicates a fission event.

Figure 2.1 shows an example of the simulation process, sampled in order to verify correct functioning. Throughout the simulation, starting from the pink shaded neutron illustrated at the centre: all paths are limited to the NNs; no neutrons are absorbed, as anticipated – as per Table 2.1 – the expected value is $1/0.005$ or 1 in 200 steps; the starting neutron lands on 20 moderator cells before being thermalised – though expected from a probabilistic sample – it is slightly longer than the expected value of 12.5 steps or $1/0.08$; after 28 generation steps, upon being thermalised it enters a fuel cell and undergoes fission with two neutrons produced; both of the fission neutrons diffuse legally until $N = 90$ steps, with one neutron escaping at the boundary cell.

2.2 Simulation Algorithm Overview

The Monte Carlo algorithm written in Python is used to operate on a arbitrarily configured pile grid of m starting neutron(s). It works by scanning and iterating through every cell (from top-left to bottom-right), computing neutron transportation walk positions for all neutrons in said cell, based on a pseudo-random number generator provided by the `numpy.random` module [6]. Whilst it scans and operates the grid, it records the generated movement positions onto a temporary array – until all the cells in the grid have been processed. At the end of one full scan, the temporary array elements are added onto the main grid array tally, with the former temporary array at such point being reset for the next step. This way, for every generation – or one whole "scan-operation" of the grid – each neutron will have only done one random walk, with their possible nuclear interactions being determined through arbitrary expected-value probabilities assigned in the algorithm's preamble setting. Whilst the simulation generations run their course, a multitude of other tallies on physical quantities are also being recorded at every step, in the domain of each cell. These include: neutron speed labels (fast or slow), energy outputs, cell types landed on, and the types of nuclear interaction events.

In the case of the Fig. 2.1 simulation, cell-type outcome probabilities are equally split. Given the chess-boarded arrangement, a neutron has 4 fuel rod cells and 4 moderator cells at any point, apart from near the boundary cells, namely ($P(N \rightarrow {}^{235}\text{U}) = 0.5$, $P(N \rightarrow C_m) = 0.5$) where ${}^{235}\text{U}$ and C_m are fuel and moderator cells respectively. Through the Monte Carlo Method, the same simulation is repeated several dozen times and expected outcome values, e.g. the mean "cell-type landed on" for each pile element, can be extracted along with their standard errors, to compare against theoretical values.

During the algorithm's development, starting from simple configurations, multiple samples like these were analysed manually to ensure no illegal moves. Once first-principle functioning was verified, complex configurations were system-monitored through debugging statements that compare parallel tallies on a step-by-step basis, flagging any incongruities. The Python code for the project is available in the appendices and different simulation animations are available on Zenodo [7], an open-access repository. The simulation results in Fig 2.1 are consistent with the framework dynamics the project's code intended to model, with neutron interactions aligning with the expected value probabilities.

Analysis

3.1 Neutron Count over time for different Fission Probabilities

Figure 3.1 Average Neutron Count Growth over Time (generation steps) for seven different Fission Probabilities, keeping other simulation variables constant. Each of the seven profiles are simulated 10 times and averaged with the error bars depicting the standard error on the mean. The subplot shows average neutron leakage intensity (%), for the same simulation data.

Figure 3.2 Average Neutron Count Growth over Time on a Logarithmic scale of base 10, for seven different Fission Probabilities, keeping other simulation variables constant. Each of the seven profiles are simulated 10 times and averaged with the error bars depicting the standard error on the mean. The subplot shows average neutron leakage intensity (%), for the same simulation data.

When a thermalised neutron collides against a fuel cell, the project simulation code models the chance of fission occurring with arbitrarily assigned fission probabilities. Figure 3.1 shows average neutron count growth in a reactor pile as the simulation evolves over time, for seven different parameters ($p_{fission}$) – each representing the probability of fission occurring in *slow-neutron-fissile-cell* interactions. For all simulations a chess-patterned pile arrangement is used; featuring a fixed probability of absorption of $p_a = 0.005$, probability of thermalisation of $p_t = 0.08$, and an average probability for transport walks to result in "fuel-type cells" of $p_{fissile} \approx 0.50$. They use a grid size of 51×51 , with 100 initial neutrons, over simulation durations of $t = 1000$ steps. Each profile curve constitutes 10 – independent and identically distributed

– MC simulation runs, with their respective means and standard errors plotted. Figure 3.2 represents the same simulation data but with the y-axis expressed on a logarithmic scale of base 10. Additionally, each figure contains a subplot indicating the percentage of neutrons being leaked & absorbed as a function of time.

As observed in Fig. 3.1, the **neutron counts for higher fission probabilities** $p_{high} = [0.029, 0.027, 0.025, 0.023]$ are clearly exponential. These indicate *super-critical* states where each fission event cascades into more than one subsequent fission event, $k > 1$; characterised by the exponential fit, $N(t) = N_0 e^{(k-1)t}$, where N_0 is the initial neutron count. **For the** $p_{low} = 0.010$ **curve**, the neutron count remains below $N(t) \leq N_0$, linearly decreasing from step $t \approx 55$ onwards, when sufficient random walks have occurred to allow for grid leakage. As the fission likelihood is low, the amount of loss is not compensated by fission neutron generation. This curve behaves **in accordance with a sub-critical** multiplication factor, $k < 1$.

3.1.1 Criticality Profile: $p = 0.017$

Observing the same data on the log-scaled graph (Figure 3.2), the neutron count **for the** $p = 0.017$ **profile** initially grows above the starting amount, $N(t) \geq N_0$, to around $N(t) \approx 135 \pm 5$ ($\pm 3.7\%$) neutrons at step $t = 180$ ($\log_{10} N(t) \approx 2.13$), an initially moderate chain reaction state. Around $t = 180$ steps there appears to be a transition region; neutron leakage begins to catch up alongside absorption as observed in the neutron loss percentage (p_{loss}) subplot: it initially averages around $0.5\% \pm 0.2\%$ – equivalent to the defined $p_a = 0.005$ absorption probability – and then plateaus to $0.8\% \pm 0.2\%$, albeit with much propagated standard error on the mean ($\pm 25\%$).

Estimated Value vs Simulation Outcome

Multiplying neutron loss probability by the total neutron count at $t = 180$, gives an expected amount of neutron-losses of approximately, $N_l(t) = 0.008 \times 135 \approx \mathbf{1.0 (\pm 25\%) \text{ average neutrons per step}}$ – for all $p_{fission}$ curves, and likewise, for any of their 10 simulation runs. Comparing with the fission neutron generation rate, the probability of a slow neutron to cause fission upon encountering a fuel cell during a transport walk is, in this example, taken as $p_{low} = 0.017$ (a conditional probability). Given that the probability ($p_{fissile}$) of encountering a fissile cell is approximately 0.50, these yield a **joint probability of 0.0085** (for a slow neutron to undergo fission during a given random walk). Knowing the total amount of slow-neutrons present $N_s(t)$, the expected amount of fission occurrences can be approximately deduced. After 180 random walks: a majority of the starting fast-neutrons are estimated to have thermalised and accumulated in the grid; but with the slow-neutron pile compositions being diluted by the fast (fission-produced) neutrons. As seen on Figure 3.3 which illustrates the average ratio of slow neutrons to total neutrons over time, around $60\% (\pm 5\%)$ of neutrons in the pile are slow at that time. Hence, around $(0.60 \times 135 \times 0.0085) = 0.68 (\pm 6.2\%)$ fission events are expected to occur at every generation step, or namely, $\nu = 2.3$ neutrons every 1.4 ($1/0.68$) generations steps. In this scenario of $\mathbf{1.64 \pm 6.2\% (2.3/1.4) \text{ fission neutrons}}$ being generated **and** $\mathbf{1.0 \pm 25\% \text{ average neutrons being lost}}$ respectively per step – over a large enough random walk

span – the state is super-critical. However looking at Fig. 3.2; since logarithmic scales denote exponential growth as straight lines and constant growth as flat gradients, the simulation's data strongly suggests that **the curve $p_{low} = 0.017$ is critical**. This variability stems from the stochastic nature of fission processes – although the sampled mean neutron count at each time step may be close to the true population mean of the 10 simulation runs, the standard deviation of the individual runs could reveal significantly high dispersions, especially since the neutron leakage is of very small sample magnitude compared to the total neutron count.

3.1.2 Full Leakage Transition

For a 51x51 grid size, the shortest path a neutron can take to exit the square pile is a straight-line trajectory of 25 steps. However the subplot in Fig. 3.2 shows that the average threshold where leakage becomes noticeable, occurs at approximately $t = 50$ steps (twice the minimum). Thereafter, the 'loss intensity' subplot only reaches a maximum after the transition phase – i.e. since the overall system probability of a random walk to result in a boundary cell is constant, in order for the leakage rate to achieve its maximum, sufficient random walks must have occurred so that every cell nearing the boundary is consistently occupied throughout every transition step (a uniform spatial flux distribution must be reached).

3.1.3 Neutron Production and Loss Intensity

As $N(t)$ grows exponentially, $N(t) = e^{(k-1)t}$, the rate of change on a log scale equates to:

$$\frac{d \log N(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{N(t)} \cdot N_0 k e^{(k-1)t} = (k-1).$$

As indicated by the two distinct gradients on the curve (around $t = 200$), there is an apparent decrease in the rate of exponential growth about the transition phase. This 'levelling down' effect appears to be present for all critical ($p_{fission}$) curves. This seems to suggest that this transition is when neutron production rates become offset by the higher values of leakage rates.

Reproduction factors, from before and after the transition phases, are obtained below by dividing the net amount of neutrons preserved in a generation step, with the corresponding amount in a previous one. The two neutron count points for each distinct gradient, are obtained by translating from the logarithmic values. Using these along with, the probability that a neutron interaction results in fission ($(p_{fission}) \times (p_{fissile} = 0.5)$), and $\nu = 2.3$; the expected number of neutrons generated is obtained. To find the expected leakage amount, the product between, the neutron count and corresponding p_{loss} rates that coincide with the gradient region, are taken. For $p = 0.029$:

- $\log_{10}N(0) = 2.00$ and $\log_{10}N(150) = 2.32$, where $p_{loss} = 0.0060$), corresponding neutron counts 100 and 209;

- ($\log_{10}N(t+400) = 2.78$ and $\log_{10}N(t+550) = 3.00$, where $p_{loss} = 0.0075$), corresponding neutron counts 602 and 1000;

The k_1 & k_2 for profile curves ($p = 0.029$) for example, are 2.1 and 1.7 respectively. In the early stages, each neutron produced through fission leads to the production of 2.1 neutrons capable of continuing the chain reaction; as leakage is fully introduced, the exponentiation of neutron count grows at a lesser magnitude, with the k-factor reducing to 1.7. Similarly for ($p = 0.025$), initial and subsequent k-factors of 1.6 and 1.3 were obtained respectively.

3.2 Slow Neutron Count Composition over Time

Figure 3.3 Evolution of the Average Slow Neutron Composition over 400 Time Steps. Grid size of 51×51 and an initial neutron count of 100, repeated for 100 runs to obtain the average and standard error on the mean."

Figure 3.3 represents the average slow neutron composition percentage as a function of time, for fission probability $p_{fission} = 0.017$. At first the pile initiates with 100 starting fast neutrons; given the thermalisation probability of $p_t = 0.08$, as mentioned before, a neutron must pass through an expected amount of 12.5 moderator cells before being thermalised ($1/0.08$). Given that the data is simulated for a chess-board arrangement pile, 50% of walks are expected to be of thermalising potential, and hence by 25 steps (12.5×2) most of the fast neutrons are expected to have thermalised. Observing from the plot, at $N_s(25) \approx 50\%$ of fast neutrons are now slow hence confirming the expected results (leakage and fission at those stages are of minimal influence).

3.3 Neutron Count over time for different Grid Sizes ($p = 0.017$)

Amongst the fission probabilities, $p = [0.017]$ is the most suitable control parameter to base the further parametric analyses on. As evidenced by the near horizontal log curve, this system operates in a near *critical state* ($k \approx 1$), yet with enough margin to prevent transition into *subcriticality*. This critical value configuration establishes a suitable environment to investigate the impact different parameters have on reactor performance. Small adjustments to reactor controls in critical systems have pronounced effects, especially in non-steady states, as changes are amplified through the exponential dynamics.

As observed from Figure 3.4, the profile of grid size 51×51 remains just about a steady-state system with its constant neutron count signifying criticality. Two trends on either side of the grid variations are observed. As the simulations are performed on decreasing grids, the chain reactions become subdued, eventually coming to a halt. For the 15×15 grid size e.g. after an amount of steps corresponding to around two times its size, all neutrons have escaped the reactor core. Likewise the same trend is observed for the 21×21 profile curve, only yet, less exponentially. It appears that during this transition region, even slight marginal increases in grid sizes allow for fission to pick up pace (once neutron inducers have thermalised to cause fission), making it possible to offset leakage at greater rates. On the other hand, the reverse relationship is also the case for increasing grid sizes. Consider the 81×81 pile profile against the critical curve: in the same number of time steps at say, $t = 800$, and for the same simulation configuration, the larger grid is composed of around double the neutron counts. This straight-forwardly suggests what an effect the 'benefit' of having a larger grid size has meant on the amount of neutrons that can reach the boundary — of course, after an amount of steps of around 10 times the grid sizes, all neutrons are made possible to escape, but however, not at the same expected intensities. This aligns well with the surface to volume ratio theory. As grid size increases, the perimeter grows by a factor of L , but the area — where fission takes place — grows by a factor of L^2 . Hence, for successively increasing grid size, less leakage is observed.

Figure 3.4 Average Neutron Count in a simulation over 1000 generation steps (of fission probability $p_{fission} = 0.017$), for different grid sizes. The simulation starts with 100 neutrons, each curve is simulated with 10 repetitions, with the error bars showing the standard error of the mean

3.4 Neutron Count over time for different Grid Arrangements ($p = 0.017$ & 51 grid size)

The assembly of a reactor, that is the geometry between the moderator and fuel cells within the pile, has its effect on the the neutron reproduction factor. As illustrated in Figure 3.5, in the chess-board arrangement, a neutron undergoing random walks passes through regions that are homogeneous, that is, the cell components happen to be more evenly mixed across. On the other hand, take the concentric ring example where layers of moderator-to-fuel cells alternate for increasing radii. In the former, once a neutron enters a moderator region, it is more likely to undergo moderation faster, but it is also more likely to be absorbed before resulting in any fission, within that time span. Hence Figure 4.6, represents these three different reactor arrangements for the same criticality configuration from before. The ring arrangement results in slightly smaller neutron count possibly because more neutrons are absorbed within the bouncing inside regions. However the difference for a concentric ring arrangement of width 3 is stark, this effect becomes dramatic, terminating the chain reaction fairly quickly.

Figure 3.5 Possible geometrical-arrangements for a reactor's pile cross-section. The left grid is a chess-board arrangement, the middle and right grids are concentric ring arrangements of cell widths, 1 and 3, respectively

Figure 3.6 Neutron Count Evolution for a chess-board arrangement

Figure 3.7 Neutron Count Evolution for a concentric rings arrangement of width 1

Figure 3.8 Neutron Count Evolution for a concentric rings arrangement of width 3

CHAPTER 4

Computation Times

Figure 4.1 Computation times as a function of Starting Neurons

Figure 4.2 Computation time as a function of grid sizes for varying starting neutron amounts

Figure 4.3 Computation time as a function of grid sizes for varying simulation generation amounts

CHAPTER 5

Conclusion and Future Work

Actual fission reactions are more complex due to variable factors such as decay products, neutron poisons, and delayed neutrons. The presence of decay products such as Thorium and Protactinium for example in Uranium 235 reactions, have higher neutron absorption rates, resulting in time-varying transition probabilities as the system evolves, or namely non-stationary Markov Chains. In the scope of this project, parameter probabilities that defined neutron interactions remained constant. Namely, the chain reactions in this project, consisted of a series of "Markov Chains" where outcome probabilities only depended on the predecessor state. Non-stationary systems, are much more reflective of real reactor dynamics as it includes all the aforementioned factors, which introduce even greater statistical variances and unpredictability. Hence in order to accurately estimate Monte Carlo outcomes in such systems, much larger amount of repetitions are required to reduce the standard error on the mean, as well as much more parametric analysis relations to be modelled with respect with another. The computational resources available to this project, would not allow for such complex system computations, however codes like the Monte Carlo N-Particle Transport model, developed by Los Alamos Laboratory effectively achieves this.

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